

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Los Angeles
Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia

A KNOWLEDGE-BASED APPROACH TO INCREASE THE UPTAKE OF THE
INFLUENZA VACCINE IN PREGNANCY

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Purpose and Objectives: The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to increase knowledge on the safety and effectiveness of the influenza vaccine among the staff in a large hospital in Southern California with the goal of increasing its uptake among pregnant patients. The project aims were to a) assess staff knowledge about the influenza vaccine's safety and efficacy, b) evaluate staff attitudes and practices in recommending the vaccine, and c) examine changes in vaccine administrations before and after the intervention. **Background:** Contracting the influenza virus during pregnancy poses significant risks to the pregnant patient and the unborn child. While any pregnant individual can be affected by influenza, those who are not vaccinated face a sixfold increase in the risk of hospitalization, admission to the intensive care unit, pneumonia, and mortality. Research highlights concerns about vaccine safety and efficacy, vaccine hesitancy, and ineffective uptake strategies as contributors to low influenza vaccine uptake. Research also suggests that pregnant patients who received vaccine education from their providers were more likely to receive the influenza vaccine. **Methodology:** The study utilized a pretest-posttest design to measure the changes in staff knowledge, attitudes, vaccine recommendation practices, and vaccination rates before and after completing an educational session. The project took place at an obstetrics clinic in a large tertiary hospital in Southern California, with 139 eligible healthcare provider participants. **Results:** Eight participants completed the pretest, intervention, and posttest. The mean difference between the pre-and post-test scores was not significant ($t = -1.94$, $p = 0.093$). However, the mean difference between the 2022 and 2023 vaccine administrations was significant ($t = -9.96$, $p < 0.001$). The weekly average number of influenza vaccinations administered increased from 24 in 2022 to 126 in 2023, as shown by a c-chart. **Conclusion:** Implementing strategies to address persistent barriers to flu vaccine uptake among pregnant patients is crucial. Providing educational material to meet specific knowledge gaps or practices among staff members is also imperative.

Keywords: Influenza vaccine, pregnancy, influenza virus, vaccine hesitancy, safety and efficacy, staff knowledge

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Background

The influenza (flu) virus, if contracted while pregnant, can render severe consequences for the mother and her unborn child (O’Leary et al., 2019). Approximately 49% of pregnant patients received the flu vaccine during the 2021-2022 flu season in the United States (U.S.), a six percent decrease from the 2020-2021 flu season (Kahn et al., 2022). Both flu seasons fell short of the Healthy People 2020 goal of 80% coverage for pregnant patients (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services [HHS], n.d.). The flu is characterized as an acute respiratory disease caused by one of many strains of the influenza virus (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2022b). Although the flu can cause illness in any pregnant person, unvaccinated pregnant patients have a six times higher risk of hospitalization, intensive care unit (ICU) admission, pneumonia, and death. (Quach et al., 2020; Thompson et al., 2019). Unvaccinated pregnant patients with comorbidities such as obesity, diabetes, and hypertension are at an even higher risk of complications. Pregnant patients also account for one percent of hospitalizations in the U.S. and almost six percent of deaths associated with the flu virus (Mertz et al., 2019).

Health organizations like the CDC (2022a), the World Health Organization (WHO, 2023), and the American College of Obstetrics and Gynecology (ACOG Committee, 2018) recommend the flu vaccine during pregnancy. The flu vaccine is safe and effective in preventing severe illness or the flu and can be given in any trimester (ACOG Committee, 2018). According to Lu et al. (2021), the number of preterm and very preterm births in vaccinated pregnant patients was significantly lower than in non-vaccinated patients. In addition, the authors found no increase in stillbirth, congenital disabilities, or admission to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) in vaccinated pregnant patients. Apgar scores of less than seven at five minutes of life,

low birth weight, very low birth weight, and small for gestational age (SGA) infants were also lower in pregnant patients who received the flu vaccine (Lu et al., 2021). Additionally, infants of vaccinated patients benefit from passive immunity, which offers protection until they can be vaccinated at six months old (Lu et al., 2021).

Although the flu vaccine has many benefits for the patient and infant, one in twelve expectant patients is vaccine-hesitant (Cunningham et al., 2018). Dudley et al. (2022) state that vaccine knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs may contribute to vaccine hesitancy. The lack of communication between the provider and patient regarding the safety and efficacy of the vaccine is attributed to low vaccination administration among pregnant patients (Lu et al., 2021). A lack of knowledge about the safety and efficacy of the flu vaccine in pregnancy can contribute to vaccine hesitancy.

Data shows that 26% of first-time pregnant patients reported not having enough information to make an informed decision about receiving the flu vaccine (Dudley et al., 2020). Patients report receiving flu vaccine information from social media and other internet sources instead of their obstetric (OB) providers (Dudley et al., 2020). A lack of provider knowledge about vaccine recommendations, safety, and efficacy can contribute to vaccine hesitancy (Adeyanju et al., 2021). Similarly, provider beliefs can hinder and create barriers preventing proper counseling. Wilson et al. (2019) provided insight as to why vaccine hesitancy may exist. The authors discovered that access to care, healthcare rhetoric, community and family influence, provider views toward vaccines, and a lack of trust between the patient and provider contributed to vaccine hesitancy (Wilson et al., 2019).

Problem Statement

Kaiser Permanente Fontana Medical Center (FMC) is one of 13 Kaiser Permanente Hospitals in Southern California. FMC is a busy obstetrics and gynecology (OB/ GYN) clinic where Medical Doctors (MDs), Certified Nurse-Midwives (CNMs), Physician Assistants (PAs), and Nurse Practitioners (NPs) provide care to approximately 500 patients daily. The administration of flu vaccines is a proactive encounter measured as a part of the clinic's performance measures. The current daily target goal for the OB/GYN clinic is to administer about 240 flu vaccines. However, the daily flu vaccination rate has fallen short of this goal, with only 50 to 100 administrations per day. The yearly target vaccination rate from January 2022 to December 2022 was 55%. During that timeframe, there were 47,264 opportunities to administer the flu vaccine, with only 8,426 successful injections achieved. At year's end, the FMC OB/GYN clinic only reached 18% of the target goal.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to provide education to MDs, CNMs, NPs, PAs, Registered Nurses (RNs), Licensed Vocational Nurses (LVNs), and Medical Assistants (MAs) on the flu vaccine safety and effectiveness to help increase the flu vaccine uptake among pregnant patients. The aims of this DNP project were to a) assess staff knowledge about the safety and efficacy of the flu vaccine before and after the intervention, b) assess staff attitudes and recommendation practices pertaining to the flu vaccine, and c) assess the change in vaccine administrations before and after the intervention.

Supporting Framework

Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care

Supporting frameworks are essential to evidence-based practice (EBP) projects. These frameworks serve as a step-by-step process to guide EBP projects from idea development through implementation, evaluation, and dissemination. The Iowa Model of Research-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care, which was first developed and utilized in 1994, is a fusion between the Quality Assurance Model Using Research (QAMUR) and Roger's Diffusion on Innovations Theory (Hanrahan et al., 2019; Titler et al., 2001). The Iowa Model was developed by the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics (UIHC) as a tool to guide the steps of integrating research findings into practice to improve patient care (Titler et al., 2001). The Iowa Model has undergone several revisions recently, including a name change from the Iowa Model of Research-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care to the Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care by incorporating feedback loops (Titler et al., 2001). The Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care, more commonly known as the Iowa Model, is a multi-step framework utilized by many healthcare institutions worldwide (Buckwalter et al., 2017). In 2012, the Iowa Collaborative was instituted to address the need for further revisions and validation (Hanrahan et al., 2019). Subsequently, a revised Iowa model was created to allow for a more substantial data analysis and literature review (Buckwalter et al., 2017). Additionally, due to the new revisions by the Iowa Collaborative, the model experienced another name change and is now called the Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care (Buckwalter et al., 2017). This scholarly DNP project used the step-by-step guidance of the Iowa Model Revised (Appendix A) to increase the flu vaccine uptake in pregnant patients.

The Iowa Model has been used extensively to guide EBP projects in various healthcare settings, and its effectiveness is well documented. The systematic approach used by the Iowa Model Revised is necessary to assess the impact of EBP on outcomes (Buckwalter et al., 2017). Cohen et al. (2022) used the Iowa Model because of the applicability and use of teams during implementation. Similarly, Laures et al. (2021) successfully used the Iowa Model to support the implementation of their algorithm to create a positive patient impact.

The Iowa Model has seven steps and three decision points to guide EBP projects. The first step of the Iowa Model Revised is to identify triggering issues/opportunities by determining whether clinical or patient problems exist. For this DNP project, both clinical and patient problems existed. The problem for this OB/GYN clinic in the author's practice setting was to increase the flu vaccine administration in pregnant patients. Following problem identification, the second step of the Iowa Model called for developing a clinical question or purpose. This DNP project aimed to increase the flu vaccine uptake in pregnant patients. After the purpose was stated, the first decision point with feedback loops guides the user to determine whether the topic was a priority and whether to continue or revert to the beginning. The identified problem was a priority for the organization and department as a part of the preventative care model. Once the problem was determined to be a priority for the organization, the third step was to form a multidisciplinary team. The team for this DNP project consisted of a team lead, the Department Chief, the Assistant Department Chiefs, the Department Administrator (DA), the Assistant Department Administrator (ADA), MDs, CNMs, NPs, PAs, RNs, LVNs, MAs, and data consultants. Not all stakeholders need to be involved in the project, but all stakeholders should believe in the project (Buckwalter et al., 2017).

In step four of the Iowa Model Revised, the body of evidence was assembled, appraised, and synthesized to determine if the body of evidence is sufficient to implement practice change. After completing a literature review, the next decision point was to determine if the evidence was sufficient. Research should be conducted when the evidence is insufficient (Buckwalter et al., 2017). If the evidence is adequate, the next step is to design and pilot the practice change.

Step five of the Iowa Model Revised involved designing and piloting change. In step five, there was patient engagement, consideration of resources, approvals and limitations, development of protocols, and plan evaluation. Additionally, staff development, baseline data collection, and the development of an implementation plan were done. During the initial process of this DNP project, staff was provided with a pre-education survey about the safety and efficacy of the flu vaccine, attitudes, and recommendation practices about the flu vaccine. Next, an educational PowerPoint presentation about the safety and efficacy of the flu vaccine was provided during the weekly staff meetings during weeks one and two of the project. After staff education was provided, a post-education survey was utilized to assess the staff's knowledge about the safety and efficacy of the flu vaccine, attitudes, and recommendation practices about the flu vaccine. At patient appointments, the flu vaccine was ordered unless contraindicated. Once the flu vaccine was ordered, the vaccine was offered to all patients. If the patient declined the vaccine, the patient received a handout stating evidence about the flu and the safety and efficacy of the vaccine.

The last decision point asked if the change was appropriate for adoption into practice within the organization. If the change was appropriate, as evidenced by an increase in flu vaccine administration, the sixth and seventh steps in the Iowa Model Revised were to integrate and sustain the practice change and disseminate the results. The seventh step may go beyond the

timeline for this DNP project. However, the proposed change will be disseminated if the training, interventions, and implementation strategies are successful.

Review of Literature

Overview

A comprehensive literature review was conducted, and articles related to flu vaccination in pregnancy and strategies to increase flu vaccine uptake in pregnant patients were identified. The search for relevant and current publications was conducted in the Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL) and PubMed medical subject headings (MeSH). The search terms used for the CINAHL literature search included: “MH influenza vaccine,” “MH vaccination/PF,” “vaccine hesitancy,” “vaccine refusal,” “pregnancy,” “pregnant,” “influenza vaccine,” “influenza vaccination,” and “flu vaccine.” The search terms used for the PubMed literature search included: “vaccine hesitancy,” “pregnancy,” and “flu vaccine.”

The search was limited to peer-reviewed articles, published in English between 2018 and 2023. Publications were excluded if the focus was not on pregnant patients and the flu vaccine. The MeSH terms “MH influenza” OR “MH Vaccination/PF” yielded 135 publications. The search terms “vaccine hesitancy” or “vaccine refusal” resulted in 126 publications. The search using “pregnancy,” “pregnant,” “influenza vaccine,” “influenza vaccination,” or “flu vaccine” resulted in 169 publications. The search terms “flu vaccine” and “pregnancy” resulted in 95 publications. The terms “pregnancy,” “pregnant,” and “influenza vaccine,” “influenza vaccination,” “flu vaccine,” and “safety and efficacy” resulted in 10 publications. The search terms “vaccine hesitancy” and “pregnancy” resulted in 103 publications. Lastly, the search terms “education” and “flu vaccine” or “influenza vaccine” or “flu shot” and “compliance” or “adherence” resulted in five publications. In addition to searching electronic databases, hand-searching was conducted to identify additional publications not identified in the electronic literature searches. After removing irrelevant and duplicate publications, 15 articles were chosen

based on content and relevance to the topic of this project (Appendices C & D). Of these, four were systematic reviews and meta-analyses (Alipanah et al., 2018; Quach et al., 2020; Lu et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2018); two were systematic reviews (Adeyanju et al., 2021; Omer et al., 2020), six were cohort studies (Bartolo et al., 2019; Dudley et al., 2020; O’Leary et al., 2019; Robinson, Obery, van Boxmeer, et al., 2022; Robinson, Van Boxmeer, Tilson et al., 2022; Thompson et al., 2019), one was a quasi-experimental study (Ozoemena et al., 2019), another one was a cross-sectional observational study (D’Alessandro et al., 2018), and one was a Committee Opinion (ACOG Committee, 2018).

The reviewed literature emphasized the importance of the flu vaccine in pregnancy. Although the vaccine benefits the health of the mother and the infant, flu vaccine uptake remains low due to concerns about vaccine safety and efficacy, vaccine hesitancy, and ineffective uptake strategies. To help combat some of the concerns regarding the flu vaccine, literature shows patient education by healthcare providers can improve vaccine uptake during pregnancy (Alipanah et al., 2018).

Safety and Efficacy

The safety and efficacy of vaccines are essential when caring for pregnant patients. The flu vaccine is recommended yearly between October and May for individuals six months and over. It should be administered during any trimester of pregnancy and to any woman of childbearing age who plans to get pregnant or will be pregnant during the flu season (ACOG, 2018; Arora & Lakshmi, 2021; CDC, 2022a; Grohskopf et al., 2018; Nypaver et al., 2021; Psarris et al., 2019). Side effects from administering vaccines can occur anytime; however, pain and redness at the injection site are most common (Nypaver et al., 2021; Psarris et al., 2019).

Although there can be adverse side effects to receiving the flu vaccine, the benefits outweigh the risks (Arora & Lakshmi, 2021; Psarris et al., 2019).

The flu vaccine is administered via an intramuscular injection in a live attenuated or inactivated vaccine. However, the inactivated vaccine is the only one safe during pregnancy because it does not cause harm to the fetus (ACOG Committee, 2018; Arora & Lakshmi, 2021; Kroger et al., 2023). The flu vaccine, with an effective rate between 38%-60%, has been shown to prevent severe illness and hospitalization during pregnancy (Arora & Lakshmi, 2021; Grohskopf et al., 2018). Maternal hospitalizations with flu vaccine administration can be decreased by as much as 40% (Thompson et al., 2019). Studies have also shown that flu vaccine administration was associated with a decrease in severe illness and complications such as an increased risk of pneumonia, respiratory failure, stillbirth, and death during pregnancy (Psarris et al., 2019; Quach et al., 2020; Robinson, Obery, van Boxmeer, et al., 2022; Robinson, Van Boxmeer, Tilson, et al., 2022, Thompson et al., 2019).

Not only does the flu vaccine have maternal benefits, but it also has fetal benefits. Studies have shown that the flu vaccine is safe for breastfeeding (ACOG Committee, 2018; Arora & Lakshmi, 2021; Kroger et al., 2023; Nypaver et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2018). At the same time, the vaccine offers passive immunity to the fetus through the placenta (ACOG Committee, 2018; Arora & Lakshmi, 2021; Grohskopf et al., 2018; Kahn et al., 2022; Lindley et al., 2019; Lu et al., 2021; Nypaver et al., 2021; Sperling & Riley, 2018). Similarly, the vaccine offers immunity until the infant can be immunized at six months old (ACOG Committee, 2018; Arora & Lakshmi, 2021; Kahn et al., 2022; Lindley et al., 2019; Lu et al., 2021; Nypaver et al., 2021; Omer et al., 2020; Psarris et al., 2019; Sperling & Riley, 2018). In pregnant patients who were vaccinated, there was a significant reduction in the risk of preterm and very preterm birth (Lu et al., 2021;

Omer et al., 2020; Sperling & Riley, 2018; Zhang et al., 2018). Additionally, congenital disabilities, NICU admissions, low birth weight, very low birth weight, and SGA infants were also lower (Lu et al., 2021; Omer et al., 2020; Sperling & Riley, 2018; Zhang et al., 2018). This project will address this gap by discussing the benefits and risks of flu vaccine administration in pregnancy and providing evidence-based practice education material at each visit.

Vaccine Hesitancy

The World Health Organization (2019) defines vaccine hesitancy as “the reluctance or refusal to vaccinate despite the availability of vaccines threatens to reverse progress made in tackling vaccine-preventable diseases” (Vaccine hesitancy section, para. 1). Vaccine hesitancy is one of many barriers attributed to the low flu vaccine rate during pregnancy. A systematic review of 11 studies involving 17,041 pregnant patients concluded that some patients generally have negative connotations about vaccines, leading to vaccine hesitancy (Adeyanju et al., 2021). Additionally, some patients were influenced by conspiracy theories, further contributing to the problem (Adeyanju et al., 2021). Another reason for flu vaccine hesitancy is a lack of knowledge regarding the benefits and adverse effects of the vaccine (Bartolo et al., 2019; Dudley et al., 2020; Nypaver et al., 2021). Studies have shown that pregnant patients perceived that the vaccine will harm the fetus (Adeyanju et al., 2021; O’Leary et al., 2019). Patients also perceived that the flu was not as severe as it is; therefore, they did not get the vaccine (Adeyanju et al., 2021). However, the most common reason patients hesitated to receive the vaccine was a lack of recommendation and information from their healthcare provider (Adeyanju et al., 2021; Bartolo et al., 2019; Lindley et al., 2019; Nypaver et al., 2021; O’Leary et al., 2019). This project will target this gap by increasing provider knowledge and emphasizing the importance of recommending the vaccine.

Strategies to Increase Vaccine Uptake by Pregnant Patients

As healthcare providers, finding ways to improve vaccine uptake in pregnancy is important. As challenging as this task may be, a simple strategy to improve vaccine uptake involves asking or recommending the vaccine to the patient. The aforementioned systematic review (Adeyanju et al., 2021) concluded that patients were unaware of the vaccine recommendation during pregnancy or were not offered the vaccine. Another strategy to help with vaccine uptake is initiating standing order protocols to ensure that patients can be vaccinated (Nypaver et al., 2021; O’Leary et al., 2019). Patient education should be done at every prenatal appointment as this will help ensure that patients receive evidence-based information about the flu vaccine (Nypaver et al., 2021; Quach et al., 2020). Additionally, patient reminders should be sent via multimedia sources regarding education and flu vaccine administration (Nypaver et al., 2021). As providers, we must always make a concerted effort to keep ourselves informed by keeping current with the current evidence to provide the best care to our patients (Dudley et al., 2020).

Improving Patient Outcomes with Patient Education

Staff education is an effective tool in preventative healthcare and provides staff with the most up-to-date EBP to counsel patients. Pregnant patients who received vaccine education from their providers were more likely to receive the flu vaccine (D’Alessandro et al., 2018). Similarly, a systematic review and meta-analysis of 129 studies concluded that patient education, both written and oral, was associated with better patient outcomes (Alipanah et al., 2018). On the other hand, educational interventions have also been shown to have a positive effect on health outcomes and disease prevention (Ozoemena et al., 2019). Providers are patients’ most trusted sources of medical information (D’Alessandro et al., 2018). Educating patients during their

appointments about vaccines is crucial as it helps dispel myths that could negatively affect their health. This project was designed to lessen this gap by preparing staff to educate appropriately and counsel patients about the flu vaccine.

Conclusion

In this vulnerable population, vaccine administration is a constant barrier for providers (Nypaver et al., 2021). Taken together, studies included in this review provide compelling evidence to support the safety and efficacy of administering the flu vaccine during pregnancy for both the mother and the infant. However, many pregnant patients do not take the vaccine. Barriers to taking the flu vaccine by pregnant patients include a lack of knowledge of the safety and efficacy of the vaccine and a lack of information provided by providers, both of which contribute to increasing hesitancy among pregnant patients (Adeyanju et al., 2021; Dudley et al., 2020; Wilson et al., 2019). In contrast, patient education in conjunction with the provider's recommendation for the flu vaccine can positively affect the mother and her unborn child. This project will aim to increase staff knowledge about the flu vaccine to increase vaccine uptake in pregnancy.

Methods

This Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project aimed to educate MDs, CNMs, NPs, PAs, RNs, LVNs, and Medical MAs on the flu vaccine safety and effectiveness to help increase the flu vaccine uptake among pregnant patients. This DNP project examined if increasing staff knowledge about the safety and efficacy of the flu vaccine will increase the flu vaccine uptake in pregnant patients. The aims of this DNP project were to a) assess staff knowledge about the safety and efficacy of the flu vaccine before and after the intervention, b) assess staff attitudes and recommendation practices pertaining to the flu vaccine, and c) assess the change in vaccine administrations before and after the intervention.

Design

This EBP DNP project utilized the pretest-posttest design to assess staff knowledge, attitudes, and recommendation practices before and after implementing an educational session. The Iowa Model Revised was used to guide the steps of this DNP project. The Iowa Model Revised was chosen for this DNP project because of its systematic approach to guiding evidence-based practice projects and documented effectiveness in healthcare settings.

Setting

This DNP project was implemented at a large tertiary hospital in Southern California's San Bernardino Service Area that serves medically underserved communities. The OB/GYN clinic in Fontana serves approximately 500 patients daily. These patients are cared for by MDs, CNMs, NPs, and PAs, as well as support staff, including RNs, LVNs, and MAs. The OB/GYN clinic is on three separate floors and consists of different modules where patients are seen by their providers. Also located within the OB/GYN clinic are the Maternal-Fetal Medicine and Reproductive Endocrinology and Infertility departments.

Participants

All OB/GYN clinic staff who cared for pregnant patients during the specified timeframe (n= 139) were invited to participate in the study. These include 59 MDs, six NPs, 11 CNMs (excludes team lead), one PA, 11 RNs, 15 LVNs, and 36 MAs. The participants were invited to participate in the study by e-mail (Appendix E).

Institutional Review Board Approval

The OB/GYN DA at Kaiser Permanente-Fontana Medical Center provided a letter of support (Appendix F) to conduct the project in the department. The proposal was submitted to the Kaiser Permanente and California State University-Fullerton (CSUF) Institution Review Boards (IRBs) and approved to conduct the project (Appendices G & H). Electronic consent to participate in the project was obtained from each participant (Appendix I), participation in this study was voluntary, and the participants were free to withdraw from participation at any time without penalty. There was minimal risk associated with participating in this survey. The risk was no more than that encountered in routine interactions with patients. No identifiable data was collected from the staff during the project. There was no financial incentive for project participation.

Implementation Plan

Project implementation began once approval was granted from the OB/GYN DA and IRB. Baseline data was obtained from the DA regarding the 2022-2023 flu vaccination administrations. The flu vaccine administration rate for the 2021-2022 flu season was 18%, below the target administration benchmark of 55% set for the department. Hence, the department could benefit from more staff education if flu vaccination administrations remain below the designated target benchmark for the 2022-2023 flu season.

A 20-minute PowerPoint was developed for staff education in collaboration with the DA. This education provided staff with an overview of the flu infection and vaccine, discussed the safety and efficacy of the vaccine, side effects and benefits of flu vaccine administration, and guidelines for and strategies to increase its administration. Once the educational PowerPoint was developed, the staff was invited to complete a 16-question online pre-education survey to assess staff knowledge, attitudes toward vaccines, and vaccine recommendation practices regarding the flu vaccine (Appendix J, Fernandes et al., 2023). The survey was created in Qualtrics and distributed via e-mail to staff before their weekly huddle meeting. At the beginning of the survey, participants were asked to create a unique identification (ID) to match the pretest and posttest surveys for data analysis. The information obtained from the survey was used as a baseline reference to assess staff knowledge. The educational PowerPoint was presented live via Teams at the weekly staff meeting during weeks one and two of the implementation process. The team lead and DA recorded attendance at the meeting. Time was allotted after each session to allow for questions staff may have had about the project. A copy of the PowerPoint was also sent to staff for future reference. After the project implementation began, bi-weekly follow-ups allowed staff to ask questions and provide feedback to help refine the process.

The project began in September 2023 and continued through April 2024 (Appendix K). Participants who attended the education session and completed the pre-education survey were asked to complete a post-education survey. The same 16-question online survey used for the pre-education survey to assess staff knowledge, attitudes toward vaccines, and vaccine recommendation practices regarding the flu vaccine was used for the post-education survey via Qualtrics (Appendix J, Fernandes et al., 2023). The survey was e-mailed to staff after the

education sessions were completed. Participants who did not receive the education or complete the pre-education survey were not to complete the post-education survey.

Data Collection

For this DNP project, a sixteen-question online survey was used to assess staff knowledge about the flu vaccine as well as questions regarding staff attitudes toward vaccines and vaccine recommendation practices regarding the flu. The four knowledge questions were answered using true/false/I do not know answers. Likewise, to assess staff attitudes regarding the flu vaccine, seven questions were answered using a 6-point Likert-like scale ranging from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree. Similarly, the remaining five questions to assess vaccine recommendation practices were answered using a 6-point Likert-like scale with the following answer choices: Always, Often, Sometimes, Never, or Not Applicable to My Practice.

Vaccine data was extracted based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. Data were extracted for all pregnant patients of any age eligible to receive the flu vaccine. Pregnant patients of any age vaccinated in the OB/GYN clinic were included. Data for non-pregnant patients and those not vaccinated in the OB/GYN clinic were excluded. The team lead created a vaccine data collection tool to collect weekly data obtained from the data consultant assigned to the project. The tool collected information on the number of patients eligible for the vaccine and the number of vaccines administered. Demographic data, including age, level of education, gender, years of experience in the profession, and years of experience with pregnant patients were collected from the staff. Appendix L shows a list of evaluation and outcome measures.

Data Analysis

Data was analyzed using Intellectus Statistics™ software. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze demographic data and the percent change in the number of patients who received the vaccine before and after the intervention. A paired *t*-test was used to analyze mean changes in staff knowledge, attitudes, and vaccine recommendations regarding the flu vaccine. Vaccine data was extracted from electronic health records by a data consultant for analysis in Intellectus Statistics™ by the team lead. A c-chart and a paired *t*-test were used to interpret the data from the vaccine data collection tool. The data was cleaned and manually entered into Intellectus Statistics™ software and Excel in preparation for data analysis. There was no identifiable information attached to any of the study participants. Data will be safeguarded for three years after the completion of the study.

Evaluation Plan

After the staff completed the pretest-posttest surveys, results obtained from the survey were used to assess the difference in knowledge before and after education. Vaccine administration data was obtained before the implementation of the project and was used as baseline vaccine data. New vaccine data was collected weekly and entered into Microsoft Excel during the project's implementation period from September 2023 through November 2023. This data was used to determine the changes in vaccine administrations.

Results

The purpose of this DNP project was to educate MDs, CNMs, NPs, PAs, RNs, LVNs, and MAs on the flu vaccine safety and effectiveness to help increase the flu vaccine uptake among pregnant patients. The aims of this DNP project were to a) assess staff knowledge about the safety and efficacy of the flu vaccine before and after the intervention, b) assess staff attitudes and recommendation practices pertaining to the flu vaccine, and c) assess the change in vaccine administrations before and after the intervention. The results of this project provide insights into staff knowledge, attitudes, recommendation practices, and the impact of an educational intervention on vaccine administration. Data for this project were collected from September 1, 2023 through November 30, 2023. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, a control chart, and paired *t*-tests. Demographics are outlined and significant findings are explained.

Patient Demographics by Age

Patient demographics were collected for September, October, and November by age group and trimester. A total of 1704 patients were vaccinated during the data collection period. September was the most commonly recorded month in the under-18 age group, constituting 58.33% of observations ($n = 7$). Similarly, September accounted for the highest frequency in the 18-24 age category, with 38.42% ($n = 78$). Within the 25-29 age group, September remained the most frequently observed month at 36.71% ($n = 163$). For the 30-34 age category, September represented the majority at 41.99% ($n = 262$). In the 35-39 age range, September was again the most prevalent month, making up 42.06% of cases ($n = 143$). Even in the 40 and older age group, September was the most frequently observed month, comprising 51.85% of occurrences ($n = 42$). The details of frequencies and percentages can be found in Appendix M.

Patient Demographics by Trimester

October emerged as the predominant month in the first trimester category, constituting the highest frequency at 59.14% (n = 411). Similarly, October was the most frequently observed month in the second trimester category, accounting for 59.35% of occurrences (n = 327). Within the third trimester category, October maintained its prominence, representing 64.41% of cases (n = 295). This finding aligns with the current advice on the optimal timing for administering the flu vaccine, which is in October (ACOG Committee, 2018). Detailed frequencies and percentages can be found in Appendix N.

Pre and Post Survey Demographics

A 16-question survey was sent via e-mail to 139 staff to assess vaccine attitudes, knowledge, and recommendation practices regarding the influenza vaccination. Both the pre- and posttest were open to participants for two weeks. At the closing of each survey period, there were 41 pretest and 13 posttest respondents. The intervention, an education module, was presented in two separate weeks, with 53 participants during week one and 55 during week two. Eight participants completed the pretest, intervention, and posttest, which were used as the sample for this project.

Participant Demographics

The age categories most commonly reported were 45-54 years old and 35-44 years old, each accounting for 37.50% with an observed frequency of 3. The highest level of education completed was most frequently a graduate or professional degree, comprising 62.50% of the responses (n = 5). Female was the predominant gender category, constituting 100% of the responses (n = 8). Regarding years of experience in the medical profession, the most frequently cited category was 15+ years, representing 50% of the responses (n = 4). Additionally, in terms

of experience caring for pregnant patients, the category with the highest frequency was 5-10 years, accounting for 37.50% of the responses ($n = 3$). Appendix O provides a detailed presentation of frequencies and percentages.

Vaccine Administration Data

The number of vaccines administered was collected weekly for 13 weeks using a data collection tool (Appendix P). Once the data was collected, a paired t -test was performed to determine whether there was a significant mean difference between the 2022 and 2023 vaccines administered. A c -chart was also created for the 2022 and 2023 administered vaccines to assess the consistency and stability of the process over time, following the guidelines set by the Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI, 2017). The c -chart is visually represented in Appendix Q.

Influenza Vaccination Administration Results

The difference between the mean values of the flu vaccines administered in 2022 and those administered in 2023 was statistically significant ($t(12) = -9.96, p < .001$). Specifically, the mean of flu vaccines administered in 2022 was significantly lower than the mean of flu vaccines administered in 2023. These findings are summarized in Appendix R, and a graphical representation of the means is displayed in Appendix S. The c -chart showed a weekly average of 24.23 vaccines administered in 2022 and an average of 126.08 vaccines administered in 2023. The fluctuation in weekly administration suggests that the process in both years likely exhibits special cause variation and lacks stability (Provost & Murray, 2011).

Pre and Post Survey Data Results

The pre-and post-survey inquiries gauged participants' understanding of vaccines, their attitudes towards vaccines, and their practices regarding vaccine recommendations. Participants responded to the four knowledge questions with options of true/false/I do not know. Similarly,

staff members expressed their attitudes toward the flu vaccine through seven questions, using a 6-point Likert-style scale ranging from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree. Furthermore, the assessment of vaccine recommendation practices consisted of five questions answered using a 6-point Likert-style scale, providing choices such as Always, Often, Sometimes, Never, or Not Applicable to My Practice.

A paired *t*-test analysis was conducted to assess whether there was a significant difference between the pre-and post-test means. Additionally, a Shapiro-Wilk test was done to investigate whether the variances in pre- and post-test questions followed a normal distribution (Razali & Wah, 2011). The test with a significance level of .05 produced non-significant findings ($W = 0.93, p = .549$). This suggests that there is no need to dismiss the normality assumption in the differences, indicating that the data met the normality assumption.

The paired *t*-test results, with a significance level of .05, showed non-significant results ($t(7) = -1.94, p = .093$). As a result, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. This suggests no significant difference in the mean scores between the pre- and posttest questions. Detailed results are provided in Appendix T, with a graphical representation of the means available in Appendix U.

Discussion

Healthcare professionals serve as the primary and most relied-upon channels for patients seeking medical information (D'Alessandro et al., 2018). The purpose of this DNP project was to educate MDs, CNMs, NPs, PAs, RNs, LVNs, and Medical MAs on the flu vaccine safety and effectiveness to help increase the flu vaccine uptake among pregnant patients. Using the Iowa Model Revised framework, this DNP project examined whether increasing staff knowledge about the safety and efficacy of the flu vaccine will increase the flu vaccine uptake in pregnant patients. The aims of this DNP project were to a) assess staff knowledge about the safety and efficacy of the flu vaccine before and after the intervention, b) assess staff attitudes and recommendation practices pertaining to the flu vaccine, and c) assess the change in vaccine administrations before and after the intervention. The results of this project provided insight into staff knowledge, attitudes, recommendation practices, and the impact of an educational intervention on vaccine administration.

This DNP project evaluated patient vaccine demographics by age and trimester, revealing interesting patterns in vaccine uptake. September emerged as a prominent month for vaccinations across various age groups, indicating potential trends in vaccination behavior. This could be because the vaccine was first offered in the clinic in September. Additionally, October appeared to be particularly significant for vaccine administration across all trimesters, suggesting a potential need for targeted interventions to capitalize on heightened vaccination rates during this period.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the acceptance of the influenza vaccine in the U.S. was significantly low, hitting a record low of 34.2%, which emphasized the ongoing difficulties with encouraging vaccination (CDC, 2020; Mercadante & Law, 2021). The comparison data on

vaccine administration for the project showed a considerable increase in the number of people who received the flu vaccine between 2022 and 2023 despite no change in staff knowledge, attitudes, and recommendations. The significant difference between vaccine administration between 2022 and 2023 is likely due to the 2022 flu season coinciding with the COVID-19 pandemic. Patients were reluctant to receive COVID-19 and flu vaccinations during this time due to safety concerns and a lack of trust (Troiano & Nardi, 2021). Additionally, the increase in flu vaccine administrations during the 2023 flu season may be attributed to bi-weekly reminders from the team lead and knowledge of project implementation. Provider recommendation may also be attributed to an uptake in vaccine administration during the 2023 flu season. Although additional research is required to determine the precise reasons for these fluctuations, the general upward trend in vaccination uptake is encouraging. It highlights the significance of continued monitoring and assessment activities.

The pre-and post-test responses for this DNP project were lower than expected. Only 5.8% (n=8) of the participants completed the pretest, intervention, and posttest that assessed staff knowledge, attitudes, and recommendations. Compared to similar studies, the sample size for this DNP project was small, rendering the findings inconsistent with current literature. Similar studies yielded sample sizes ranging from 864 to 23,500 participants (Fernandes et al., 2023; Nasiri et al., 2022; Scalia et al., 2022).

Consistent with current literature, in a systematic review of 21 studies, educational interventions were shown to increase vaccine uptake in patients (Nasiri et al., 2022). A meta-analysis of 10 randomized control trials (RCTs) used educational interventions to increase vaccine uptake (Scalia et al., 2022). The educational interventions used in the 10 RCTs were successful at increasing vaccine uptake. Therefore, a larger sample size could have facilitated a

more comprehensive evaluation of staff knowledge and attitudes in this DNP project, potentially yielding results aligning with existing literature that explains the impact of educational interventions on increased vaccine uptake. This DNP project did not show an increase in staff knowledge following an education intervention, which could be due to the small number of participants who completed this project.

Recommendations

Future research could explore the effectiveness of similar educational interventions in diverse healthcare settings and with larger sample sizes. A larger sample size would make the results more generalizable (Grove & Gray, 2019). Additionally, ongoing monitoring and evaluation of vaccination practices are essential to ensure continued improvements in vaccine uptake rates. Furthermore, ongoing monitoring and evaluation of vaccine administration data are imperative to assess the long-term sustainability of intervention effects and identify areas for further improvement.

Implications for Practice

The findings of this project have practical implications for healthcare providers and patients. Implementing mandatory staff education to increase staff knowledge, attitudes, and recommendation practices, this OB/GYN clinic may effectively promote flu vaccine uptake among pregnant patients. This can ultimately reduce the risk of flu-related complications for both mother and baby. Increasing the flu vaccination rates among pregnant patients is not an easy task for healthcare providers. It takes a multifaceted approach to increase knowledge about the safety and efficacy of the vaccine and implement strategies to improve outcomes. Finding creative ways to decrease vaccine hesitancy while improving patient outcomes through education is vital. Implementing targeted educational interventions and incorporating vaccination best practices

into routine clinical care can help maximize the impact of flu vaccination efforts in obstetric settings.

Limitations

While the project yielded valuable insights, several limitations should be acknowledged. The relatively small sample size and the single-site focus may limit the generalizability of the findings to broader healthcare settings. Additionally, relying on self-reported data for staff knowledge and attitudes introduces potential bias and may not accurately reflect actual practices. Furthermore, the short-term nature of the intervention and data collection period may not capture long-term changes in vaccination behaviors or clinic dynamics. Finally, implementing vaccine education before the start of the influenza season can help prepare staff for questions and barriers that may be encountered. Early education can help staff feel better prepared to help dispel the negative information surrounding the influenza vaccine.

Conclusion

In conclusion, both the pre-and post-test results gave valuable insights into the attitudes and behaviors of staff members concerning influenza vaccination. The impact of the intervention on staff knowledge, attitudes, and recommendations was not statistically significant, and the sample size for the DNP project was smaller than anticipated. Although this was the case, the project successfully created a foundation for future interventions and highlighted areas that require additional investigation. One example is tailoring the educational material to meet specific knowledge gaps or misconceptions among staff members.

It is crucial to build upon the findings of this project and implement targeted strategies to address persistent barriers to flu vaccine uptake among pregnant patients. This may involve ongoing staff education, standing orders, and integration of vaccination reminders into routine

clinical workflows. By adopting a comprehensive approach that addresses provider and patient perspectives, clinics can play a pivotal role in promoting vaccinations as a cornerstone of preventive care during pregnancy.

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Appendix A

Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care

The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

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Appendix B

Permission to use the Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care

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Appendix C

Literature Review Table of Evidence: CINAHL

Database: Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature(CINAHL)

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
MH influenza OR MH Vaccination/PF	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2018-2022, pregnancy	135	95	40	6
Vaccine hesitancy OR Vaccine refusal	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2018-2022, pregnancy	126	2	21	1
Pregnancy or pregnant and influenza vaccine or influenza vaccination or flu vaccine	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2018-2023, pregnancy	169	119	50	0
Pregnancy or pregnant and influenza vaccine or influenza vaccination or flu vaccine and safety and efficacy	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2018-2023, pregnancy	10	3	7	3
Education and Flu vaccine or influenza vaccine or flu shot and compliance or adherence	Peer Reviewed, English language, Publish Date: 2018-2023	5	2	3	3

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to the project topic.

Appendix D

Literature Review Table of Evidence: PubMed

Database: PubMed

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Vaccine hesitancy AND pregnancy	Peer Reviewed, English, pregnant women, 2018-2023	103	73	30	2
Flu vaccine and pregnancy	Peer Reviewed, English, pregnant women, pregnancy, 2018-2023	95	50	44	0

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to the project topic.

Appendix E

Participant Information Sheet

A Knowledge-Based Approach to Increase the Uptake of the Influenza Vaccine in Pregnancy

Dear OB/GYN Providers and Staff,

You are invited to participate in a voluntary research study titled “A Knowledge-Based Approach to Increase the Uptake of the Influenza Vaccine in Pregnancy.” Karla Hill, MSN, CNM, WHNP-BC, a Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) student at California State University, Fullerton (CSUF), will conduct this research study. Karla Hill, MSN, CNM, WHNP-BC, under the advisement of Drs. Sadeeka Al-Majid and Angela Sojobi, the DNP project committee members from the CSUF School of Nursing,

The purpose of this DNP study is to provide staff education to MDs, CNMs, NPs, PAs, RNs, LVNs, and MAs on the flu vaccine’s safety and effectiveness and create a new workflow algorithm to help increase the flu vaccine uptake among pregnant patients. There is no guarantee that you will benefit from participating in this study. The aims of this DNP project are to a) assess staff knowledge about the safety and efficacy of the flu vaccine before and after the intervention, b) assess staff attitudes and recommendation practices pertaining to the flu vaccine, and c) assess the change in vaccine administrations before and after the intervention.

If you elect to participate in this study, you will complete a 16-question electronic survey about the flu vaccine. There is no guarantee that you will benefit from participating in this study. By clicking on the survey, you are electing to participate. Your participation in this study is voluntary. You are free to withdraw from participation in this study at any time. There is minimal risk associated with your participation in this survey. The risk is no more than that encountered in routine interactions with patients. The survey should take at most 10 minutes to complete, and you may stop the survey at any time and withdraw consent to participate by exiting the electronic survey. You may also skip any question you do not want to answer. All the responses in the survey will be recorded anonymously, and data will be gathered to look for trends. Data will be kept on a password-protected KP computer with firewall software, locked in Karla Hill’s private office at Kaiser Permanente Fontana.

If you have questions about the survey, please e-mail Karla Hill, MSN, CNM, WHNP-BC, at Karla.Hill@csu.fullerton.edu or by phone at (909) 427-6279. If you have questions about your rights as a research participant or would like to report a concern or complaint about this study, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7719 or e-mail irb@fullerton.edu.

Please click on the survey link below and provide your feedback.

https://fullerton.qualtrics.com/jfe/form/SV_9t7sHFVfNYkyP4i

Thank you,

Karla Hill, MSN, CNM, WHNP-BC
Doctor of Nursing Practice Candidate
Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

Appendix F

Project Site Letter of Support

SCPMG OBGYN
 Fontana Medical Center
 San Bernardino County Area
 9958 Sierra Ave. MOB 1
 Fontana, CA 92335

Institution Approval Letter

April 18, 2023

This letter is to show that I, Hilda Ramos, MSN, RN, as the Department Administrator of the Obstetrics and Gynecology Department at Kaiser Permanente Fontana Medical Center, give permission to Karla L. Hill, DNP student, to conduct the project titled "A Knowledge-Based Approach to Increase the Uptake of the Influenza Vaccine in Pregnant Women" in the following clinic: Obstetrics and Gynecology Clinic at Kaiser Permanente Fontana Medical Center. Upon obtaining all necessary clearances from the Nursing Research Council at Kaiser Permanente Fontana Medical Center and after obtaining the necessary IRB determination/approval, the project named above lead is allowed to:

- (1) collect data relevant to their department
- (2) access necessary documents/data
- (3) conduct necessary interactions with staff/patients relevant to their project
- (4) distribute pre-and post- intervention surveys using the staff email

The project lead is responsible for ensuring that all activities related to conducting the project are in compliance with the policies that govern practice, HIPPA, and research and research-related regulations at Kaiser Permanente Fontana Medical Center and its covered entities.

If you have any questions or concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Signature:

Name: Hilda Ramos

Title: Department Administrator

Contact Information:

Hilda.X.ramos@kp.org

Appendix G

Kaiser Permanente IRB Approval

Institutional Review Board
Kaiser Permanente Southern California/Hawaii

June 21, 2023

KP Principal Investigator(s)

Karla L Hill, MSN-KPSC - Ob/Gyn
9985 Sierra Ave.. Fontana , CA 92335

Study Title: A Knowledge-Based Approach to Increase the Uptake of the Influenza Vaccine in Pregnant Women (#13602)

On **06/21/2023**, a subcommittee of the Kaiser Permanente Southern California (KPSC) Institutional Review Board (IRB) reviewed and approved your new study.

In accordance with the requirements for research activities that present no more than minimal risk to subjects set forth in 45 CFR 46.110 the study referenced above qualified for expedited review under the following research category(s):

- Category 5: Research involving materials (data, documents, records, or specimens) that have been collected, or will be collected solely for nonresearch purposes (such as medical treatment or diagnosis)

The Kaiser Permanente Southern California IRB has determined that a continuing review of this study is not required.

Study Document(s):

Karla_Hill_Data Element_Abstraction Form Template[33] 06/11/2023

A subcommittee of the Institutional Review Board determined that this study satisfies the requirements of DHHS 45 CFR 46.404, research not involving greater than minimal risk.

In accordance with 45CFR 46.116, informed consent was waived by the IRB based on the following determination(s):

- The research involves no more than minimal risk to the subjects;
- The research could not practicably be carried out without the requested waiver or alteration;
- If the research involves using identifiable private information or identifiable biospecimens, the research could not practicably be carried out without using such information or biospecimens in an identifiable format;

- The waiver or alteration will not adversely affect the rights and welfare of the subjects; and
- Whenever appropriate, the subjects or legally authorized representatives will be provided with additional pertinent information after participation.

The requirement that written Privacy Rule authorization be obtained from study participants was waived.

The Kaiser Permanente Principal Investigator (PI) is required to:

- Review the document entitled HIPAA Privacy Rule Instructions for Researchers available at http://irb.kp-scalresearch.org/5/HIPPA_Privacy_Rule_Instructions_for_Researchers.pdf
- Submit a complete final closure report of research activities.

And if applicable,

- Reach out to my SPA member or ResEvalFINSPA@kp.org to ensure a contract is in place prior to discussing or disclosing confidential information and/or data with Non-Kaiser Permanente Southern California personnel. Data types that require a contract include propriety information, business-sensitive information, de-identified or protected health information (PHI) whether it is limited or full PHI in any form (oral, written, or electronic). IRB approval does not constitute authorization to release data.
- Submit for IRB review, modifications to the study or any IRB-approved study document(s) before they are implemented **except** when necessary to eliminate apparent immediate hazards to one or more subjects. If you determine that an immediate modification is critical to eliminate hazards to one or more subjects, you must notify the IRB within five business days of having carried out such changes to your study.
- Submit Unanticipated Serious Adverse Event report(s) according to IRB policies and procedures and consistent with federal regulations.
- Submit Protocol Violation report(s) and other Unanticipated Problem Reports according to IRB policies and procedures and consistent with federal regulations.

Sincerely,

Signature applied by Isabel M Sanchez on
06/21/2023 05:51:00 PM PDT

IRB Administration

Appendix H

California State University-Fullerton IRB Approval

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON

Office of Research and Sponsored Projects

P.O. Box 6850 or 1121 N. State College Blvd., 2nd FL., Fullerton, CA 92831 / T 657-278-7719 / F 657-278-7238

APPROVAL NOTICE

*From the Institutional Review Board
California State University, Fullerton*

July 17, 2023

**From: Dr. Matt Englar-Carlson, Chair
CSUF Institutional Review Board**

To: PI: Karla Hill

Application No. HSR-22-23-460

Study Title: A Knowledge-Based Approach to Increase the Uptake of the Influenza Vaccine in Pregnant Women

Re: Initial Exempt Review

The forms you submitted to this office regarding the use of human participants in the above-referenced proposal have been reviewed by the Regulatory Compliance Coordinator and the Chair of the California State University, Fullerton, Institutional Review Board. Your proposal is determined to be Category 2.(i). Research that only includes interactions involving educational tests (cognitive, diagnostic, aptitude, achievement), survey procedures, interview procedures, or observation of public behavior (including visual or auditory recording) if at least one of the following criteria is met:

The information obtained is recorded by the investigator in such a manner that the identity of the human subjects cannot readily be ascertained, directly or through identifiers linked to the subjects;

Category 4. Secondary research for which consent is not required: Secondary research uses of identifiable private information or identifiable biospecimens, if at least one of the following criteria is met:

(i) The identifiable private information or identifiable biospecimens are publicly available;

(ii) Information, which may include information about biospecimens, is recorded by the investigator in such a manner that the identity of the human subjects cannot readily be ascertained directly or through identifiers linked to the subjects, the investigator does not contact the subjects, and the investigator will not re-identify subjects;

(iii) The research involves only information collection and analysis involving the investigator's use of identifiable health information when that use is regulated under 45 CFR parts 160 and 164, subparts A and E, for the purposes

of "health care operations" or "research" as those terms are defined at 45 CFR 164.501 or for "public health activities and purposes" as described under 45 CFR 164.512(b); or

(iv) The research is conducted by, or on behalf of, a Federal department or agency using government-generated or government-collected information obtained for nonresearch activities, if the research generates identifiable private information that is or will be maintained on information technology that is subject to and in compliance with section 208(b) of the E-Government Act of 2002, 44 U.S.C. 3501 note, if all of the identifiable private information collected, used, or generated as part of the activity will be maintained in systems of records subject to the Privacy Act of 1974, 5 U.S.C. 552a, and, if applicable, the information used in the research was collected subject to the Paperwork Reduction Act of 1995, 44 U.S.C. 3501 et seq.

The CSUF IRB has not evaluated your proposal for scientific merit, except to weigh the risk to the human participants and the aspects of the proposal related to potential risk and benefit. This approval notice does not replace any departmental or additional approvals which may be required.

In addition, all research personnel must follow the institutional safety guidelines outlined for CSUF's Presidential Directive 22. Additional information can be found in the [TITANS RETURN: COVID-19 Recovery website](#).

It is of utmost importance that you strictly adhere to the guidelines for human participants and that you follow the plan/methodology/procedures described in your research proposal. Since your proposal was determined to be exempt, there is no further review or annual renewal required by the CSUF IRB. **However, any change in protocol or consent form procedure requires re-submission to the CSUF IRB for approval prior to implementation.** Additionally, the principal investigator must promptly report, in writing, any unanticipated or adverse events causing risks to research participants or others.

Please be advised that if you are seeking external funding for this proposal, the above-reference title should match exactly with the title submitted to the funding sponsor. Any changes in project title should be submitted to the CSUF IRB prior to implementation.

By copy of this notice, the chair of your department (and/or co-investigator) is reminded that their responsibility for being informed concerning research projects involving human participants in the department, and should review all protocols of such investigations as often as needed to ensure that the project is being conducted in compliance with our institutional policies and with DHHS regulations.

The institution has an Assurance on file with the Office of Human Research Protections. The Assurance Number is FWA00015384.

Cc: IRB Office
Sadeeka Al-Majid

ADDITIONAL RESOURCES:

Withdrawal - A withdrawal submission notifies the Research Compliance Office that you no longer wish to submit your initial submission and want to withdraw the study. Withdrawn studies are marked as finalized and can no longer

be modified. You may create a withdrawal submission at any point once an initial submission has been created, until it has been approved. If the initial submission had been approved, you must create a closure submission in order to close the study if you no longer wish to conduct the research. For additional guidance, access the step-by-step instructions for [Cayuse IRB: Submitting a Withdrawal Notification](#).

Modification - If you wish to change any of the details of the study after it has been approved, you must submit a modification which must be approved before you can proceed with the changes. Modifications will only be available after initial approval is issued. Modifications will be linked with the initial application and you will make revisions to the initial application based on the modifications you are requesting. For additional guidance, access the step-by-step instructions for [Cayuse IRB: Submitting a Modification](#).

Renewal - When a study is nearing its expiration date, you must submit a renewal request in order to continue with the research. Expiration notices will be emailed from Cayuse. Renewals, like modifications, will only be available after initial approval is issued. For additional guidance, access the step-by-step instructions for [Cayuse IRB: Submitting a Renewal](#).

Incident - You must submit an incident report to inform the IRB Office of any adverse incidents, as required by your institution. Incident reports may be submitted at any time after a study has been approved, including after it has been closed. More than one incident report may be created for a given study, as needed. For additional guidance, access the step-by-step instructions for [Cayuse IRB: Submitting an Incident Report](#).

Closure - A closure submission indicates that the research is complete and will not be continuing. Closed studies are marked as finalized and can no longer be modified. For additional guidance, access the step-by-step instructions for [Cayuse IRB: Submitting a Closure Request](#).

Appendix I

Consent Form

A Knowledge-Based Approach to Increase the Uptake of the Influenza Vaccine in Pregnancy

Dear OB/GYN Providers and Staff,

You are invited to participate in a voluntary research study titled “A Knowledge-Based Approach to Increase the Uptake of the Influenza Vaccine in Pregnant Patients.” Karla Hill, MSN, CNM, WHNP-BC, a Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) student at California State University, Fullerton (CSUF), will conduct this research study. Karla Hill, MSN, CNM, WHNP-BC, under the advisement of Drs. Sadeeka Al-Majid and Angela Sojobi, the DNP project committee members from the CSUF School of Nursing.

The purpose of this DNP study is to provide staff education to MDs, CNMs, NPs, PAs, RNs, LVNs, and MAs on the flu vaccine’s safety and effectiveness and create a new workflow algorithm to help increase the flu vaccine uptake among pregnant patients. There is no guarantee that you will benefit from participating in this study. The aims of this DNP project are to a) assess staff knowledge about the safety and efficacy of the flu vaccine before and after the intervention, b) assess staff attitudes and recommendation practices pertaining to the flu vaccine and c) assess the change in vaccine administrations before and after the intervention.

If you elect to participate in this study, you will complete a 16-question electronic survey about the flu vaccine. There is no guarantee that you will benefit from participating in this study. By clicking on the survey, you are electing to participate. Your participation in this study is voluntary. You are free to withdraw from participation in this study at any time. There is minimal risk associated with your participation in this survey. The risk is no more than that encountered in routine interactions with patients. The survey should take at most 10 minutes to complete, and you may stop the survey at any time and withdraw consent to participate by exiting the electronic survey. You may also skip any question you do not want to answer. All the responses to the survey will be recorded anonymously, and data will be gathered to look for trends. Data will be kept on a password-protected KP computer with firewall software, locked in Karla Hill’s private office at Kaiser Permanente Fontana.

If you have questions about the survey, please e-mail Karla Hill, MSN, CNM, WHNP-BC, at Karla.Hill@csu.fullerton.edu or by phone at (909) 427-6279. If you have questions about your rights as a research participant or would like to report a concern or complaint about this study, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7719 or e-mail irb@fullerton.edu.

What does my consent on this form mean?

Your consent on this form means that:

- You understand the information given to you in this form
- You have been able to ask the researcher questions and state any concerns
- The researcher has responded to your questions and concerns

- You believe you understand the research study and the potential benefits and risks that are involved.

Statement of Consent:

I have carefully read and/or have had the terms used in this consent form and their significance explained to me. By clicking below, I agree that I am at least 18 years of age and agree to participate in this project. You may print this page for your records.

AGREE
 DISAGREE

Appendix J

Pre/Post Survey

Questions Assessing Vaccine Knowledge, Attitudes, and Recommendation Practices Among Healthcare Providers in an OB/GYN

Questions Assessing Vaccine Knowledge

Answer Choices: True, False, I do not know

- There is a clear link between certain vaccines and autism
- Multiple vaccines administered at a single visit overwhelm the immune system
- Vaccines should be deferred during mild illness
- Provider vaccine recommendations associated with vaccine acceptance

Questions Assessing Vaccine Attitudes

Answer Choices: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, Strongly Disagree

- I am confident in my ability to communicate with vaccine-hesitant patients
- Recommending and/or administering vaccines is within my scope of practice
- I have a responsibility to ensure that my patients are fully vaccinated
- Other providers recognize my role in vaccinating patients
- Benefits of vaccines outweigh the risks
- Influenza vaccine is effective in preventing severe disease
- Influenza infection is not severe enough to warrant annual vaccination

Questions Assessing Vaccine Recommendation Practices

Answer Choices: Always, Often, Sometimes, Never, Not Applicable to My Practice

- I routinely recommend the standard vaccines to all patients
- I routinely initiate vaccine discussions with my patients
- I review and recommend immunizations at each patient encounter
- I routinely recommend the influenza vaccine to my patients
- I routinely recommend the vaccine to pregnant patients

Note. Adapted from Fernandes et al. (2023). Used/Reprinted/Modified with permission from

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Manika Suryadevara, MD, suryadem@upstate.edu.

Appendix K

Project Timeline

Note. KP=Kaiser Permanente; CSUF=California State University-Fullerton.

Appendix L

Methods of Evaluation

Methods of Evaluations and Outcome

Outcome	Operational Definition	Method of Evaluation	Analysis
Knowledge, attitudes, & vaccine recommendations related to flu vaccine education	Pre-and Post-Education related to flu vaccine education	Knowledge Survey	Paired <i>t</i> -test
Number of patients who were administered the flu vaccine	Number of patients eligible to receive the flu vaccine	Vaccine Collection Tool	Run Chart/Paired <i>t</i> -test

Appendix M

Demographics by Age

Frequency Table for Nominal Variables

Variable	AGE					
	Under 18 (n)%	18-24 (n)%	25-29 (n)%	30-34 (n)%	35-39 (n)%	40 & Older (n)%
Month						
September	7 (58.33%)	78 (38.42%)	163 (36.71%)	262 (41.99%)	143 (42.06%)	42 (51.85%)
October	4 (33.33%)	69 (33.99%)	138 (31.08%)	204 (32.69%)	117 (34.41%)	19 (23.46%)
November	1 (8.33%)	56 (27.59%)	143 (32.21%)	158 (25.32%)	80 (23.53%)	20 (24.69%)
Total	12 (100.00%)	203 (100.00%)	444 (100.00%)	624 (100.00%)	340 (100.00%)	81 (100.00%)

Appendix N

Demographics by Trimester

Frequency Table for Nominal Variables

Variable	Trimester		
	First (n)%	Second (n)%	Third (n)%
Month			
September	18 (2.59%)	66 (11.98%)	51 (11.14%)
October	411 (59.14%)	327 (59.35%)	295 (64.41%)
November	266 (38.27%)	158 (28.68%)	112 (24.45%)
Total	695 (100.00%)	551 (100.00%)	458 (100.00%)

Note. First trimester=conception to 13 weeks 6 days; Second trimester=14 weeks 0 days to 27

weeks 6 days; Third trimester=28 weeks 0 days until delivery.

Appendix O

Participant Demographics

Demographics for the Pre and Post Test Participants

Variable	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
How old are you?		
25-34 years old	1	12.50
35-44 years old	3	37.50
45-54 years old	3	37.50
55-64 years old	1	12.50
What is the highest level of education you have completed?		
Some college, but no degree	1	12.50
Associate or technical degree	2	25.00
Graduate or professional degree (MA, MS, MBA, PhD, JD, MD, DDS, etc.)	5	62.50
What is your gender?		
Female	8	100.00
Years of experience in the medical profession?		
5-10 years	2	25.00
10-15 years	2	25.00
15+ years	4	50.00
Years of experience caring for pregnant patients?		
1-4 years	1	12.50
5-10 years	3	37.50
10-15 years	2	25.00
15+ years	2	25.00

Appendix P

Data Collection Tool

Weekly Vaccine Administration Totals

Week of Administration	Vaccines Administered	Vaccine Opportunities
	<i>n</i>	<i>n</i>
Week 1: September 4-10	145	506
Week 2: September 11-17	212	748
Week 3: September 18-24	199	699
Week 4: September 25-October 1	139	525
Week 5: October 2-8	60	255
Week 6: October 9-15	142	557
Week 7: October 16-22	140	550
Week 8: October 23-29	158	582
Week 9: October 30-November 5	116	252
Week 10: November 6-12	124	454
Week 11: November 13-19	106	491
Week 12: November 20-26	83	393
Week 13: November 27-30	80	486

Note. Number of vaccines administered (n=1704); Number of vaccine opportunities (n=6687).

Appendix Q

Administered Vaccine Data

C-Chart For 2022 vs 2023 Average of Vaccines Administered

Appendix R

Paired *t*-Test Data

Paired t-Test for the Difference Between 2022 Vaccines Administered and 2023 Vaccines Administered

2022 Vaccines Administered		2023 Vaccines Administered		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
24.23	11.29	126.08	43.99	-9.96	<.001	2.76

Note. N = 13. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 12. *d* represents Cohen's *d*.

Appendix S**Bar Plot**

The Means of 2022 Vaccines Administered and 2023 Vaccines Administered

Appendix T

Paired *t*-Test Data

Paired t-Test for the Difference Between Pre and Posttest Questions

Pretest Questions		Posttest Questions		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
3.54	0.39	3.65	0.33	-1.94	.093	0.69

Note. N = 8. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 7. *d* represents Cohen's *d*.

Appendix U

Bar Plot

The Means of Pretest and Posttest Questions

